

Dental cast and bridge numerical models for 3d printers' comparison. National scale research

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Abstract

Numerical models are of paramount importance to provide numerical test and pave the way for physical testing and validations. We want to introduce a numerical model used to test 3D printers' capabilities to produce valid and correct model.

Keywords: 3D model, verification, dental cast, teeth, dental bridge.

Introduction

Many commercial products are used nowadays in different dental facilities (1). Dental works need precision and accuracy (2). There is high uncertainty about the final results gained by these products. Many factors affect the resolution and accuracy of the printings process. Some is general, while other is peculiar to certain products. There are growing trends toward implementation of the new materials in the additive manufacturing in the dental rehabilitation and manufacturing of the dental prosthesis owing to the advancement in the chemical engineering. Same day treatments could be achieved nowadays utilizing these devices. Precision is an essential prerequisite in the whole process.

Figure 1 Permanent crowns printed with 3D printing technology

Figure 2 There are many 3D printing technologies. The resin based is the best based upon the accuracy and material properties. The first is thermoplast and second thermoset technology (3)

The resin-based technology based on the main elements

- Resin
- Printing bed
- Transparent polymer that control passage of the light to expose the resin above it where it will be stick more to the bed than this transparent polymer resulting in predictable and easier separation of he solidified resin from the transparent polymer rather than the printing bed
- The light source which could be laser or controller LED light

From where the inaccuracies are born?

Figure 3 The worst deformation is when the stage is maligned with the printing bed. This will result in unresolved distortion. Rail, bed and the printing stage should be aligned well

Figure 4 Although the bed alignment is important, but eventually it will be resolved

Figure 5 Increase in the volume increase with the layer thickness and the transparency of the used resin and the intensity of the light and the catalyzer of the resin. All will lead to an enlarged physical object. This will occur at the largest extent with the transparent resin and the least extent with the black resin due o the least transparency and resultant least light leakage and contamination

Figure 6 At raising of the printed object from the printing stage

When the printing of a layer is completed and the bed start to raise, there are 2 forces that should be considered (4)

- Release from the polymeric film
- The entry of the resin below the printed object which is directly affect by the rheological properties of the rising and the surface area of the printed object

This will put the printed object in tension status.

Accordingly, the better is to print the heaviest part at the first closer to the bed of the printing (5)

Figure 7 Return of the of the printed object to the closest position into the printing bed will displace the resin creating compression force on the printed object and supports

Figure 8 The forces will keep the printing object to b in continuous alternate stresses due to the 2 previous phenomena

The stresses that the model exposed to during printing could have a plastic deformation effect on the printed part (6). Our goal is to investigate this issue.

One of the most important features that would provide the stability of the 3d printers is the hardware, especially the use of linear rails and ball screws. Servomotors provide an extra layer of certainty. Resin tank volume is important in providing an uninterrupted consistent printing service. Heating of the bed is of paramount importance to attain consistent viscosity of the resin. The closed systems hinder the work in many times and limit the ability of the user to cope with the upcoming resins that might not be provided with the company or even prevent the more affordable alternative where the quality could be even better. Failed component is not an impossible thing to be occurred, which could be happen at any time. Locally manufactured printer will provide the best possibility to solve this issue

In order to step the first step in the road we should provide objective criteria for evaluation. We had presented the current model to fulfill this issue

For evaluation we have

- Deformational criterial, which we will discuss in this paper
- Mechanical testing which needs a separate paper
- Ancillaries

This paper is part of the support for national project of locally produced 3D printer called (Matic) by a talented prosthodontist (Dr. Bashar Muhammed Sakin)

Methods

We had presented a model derived from enlarged dental cast and bridge. The shapes are with flat surfaces in order to provide an unparallel ability to evaluate the engineering evaluation of any deformation (7). We have only 2 deformations tensile or shear. Torsional deformation is resulted from the combination of the previous dimensional instability.

No compressive distortion would be happed as the cured resin will have no compression propensity

Different Types of Stresses

Figure 9 the types of stress are clear

1- Dental cast numerical model

The thickness of the walls was 2 mm

Figure 10 We always start with numbers. This is the half of the cast base

Figure 11 The sketch had been mirrored and extruded by 10 mm

Figure 13 The final model

Figure 14 The model is hollowed with thickness of 2 mm for all walls

2- Dental bridge numerical model

The model is hollowed with thickness of 2 mm for all walls

Figure 15 The model of the bridge is derived from the previous sketch

Figure 16 This model is also numners-drevin model

Figure 17 The upper edge is 0.5mm and the upper edge is 1.5 mm which had been chosen to represent dental bridge engineeringly. The thickness of the walls was 2 mm

Figure 18 The organic shapes are extremely difficult to be aligned which could introduce another error in the comparison

Figure 19 Malalignment is highly possible which would deceive the analyzer that there is a deformation

Results and discussions

3 models will be printed in different orientations to explore this important parameter

Figure 20 The printing stage is at the roof and he crown model should be printed using the resin designed for crown and bridges

*Figure 21 The cast model should be printed with the resin designed for that purpose at the 3 angulations.
The printing bed is at the roof*

The physical models will be with a 3SHAPES scanner they produce one of the best results (8). The scanned digital models will be compared to the original CAD using online engineering tool called VOYAGER from Lumafield which British not Israeli company specialized in engineering evaluation. This will enable all the researchers to collaborate easily to the current research efficiently. The idea behind the flat surface is to catch any deformation at any level.

Figure 22 This is a comparison graph is apparent. The more value of the red color indicates the higher deviation

The deformations are most likely to be at the last layers due to the exaggeration of the deformation forces

The Fromlabs printers are one of the best 3D printers in the market nowadays and we had chosen it to be the golden standers in the terms of time and accuracy. (9)

Figure 23 The timing is very important

Figure 24 Different timing associated with different orientations

The time finished with each printer included in the comparison will be compared to the time needed by Fromlabs printer.

This is the first important aspect of evaluation and in the next paper we will discuss the mechanical properties if Almighty God will.

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Author profile

Mohammed Zahid Saadoon BDS– FKHCMS (Maxillofacial Surgery). During 2014-2024 he was involved in many researches in biomechanics and biomechatronic. He developed many theories in maxillofacial traumatology, craniofacial growth and dental implantology. He developed a unique dental implant system. He has a special interest in mechanical engineering applications in the medical and dental specialties as well as in forensic medicine. He is now working as maxillofacial surgeon in Ashty teaching hospital, largest secondary referral centers in Soran discrete at Kurdistan region / Iraq.